

Platform for EpiGenomic Research (PEGR)

A flexible management platform for reproducible epigenomic and genomic research

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ABSTRACT

Reproducibility is one of the cornerstones of scientific research. However, reproducibility has been a longtime challenge across many scientific fields [1-3]. These difficulties arise from complexities in experimental and bioinformatic workflows that diverge over time, across different operators, and often with limited versioning [4-6]. In the field of genomics, collections of massive datasets that can be parsed in many ways has added to the reproducibility challenge [7-11]. What is needed is systematic metadata capture and management software that is tailored to (epi)genomic data collection.

In general, a genomic project is composed of two distinct but interrelated components: ‘wet-bench’ biochemistry experiments and ‘dry-bench’ bioinformatic analysis. In wet-bench experiments: sample type (human tissue biopsy, yeast, etc.), reagents (catalogue number, wash buffer recipe, etc.), growth environment (log growth, % confluence, etc.), and experimental protocols (ChIP-seq, Western blot, etc.) are examples of critical metadata that need to be captured. Minor

variations in these experimental components can result in distinct experimental outcomes [12, 13]. Confounding these issues is the traditional reliance on storing experiment metadata in hand-written notebooks, which are not searchable and often incomprehensible to a third party [14]. Consequently, it can be difficult to follow and accurately reproduce an experimental protocol from start to finish.

Similarly, in bioinformatics analysis, different analytical tools, software versions, and tool parameters may generate different analytical outcomes. While progress has been made in tracking and reproducing informatic workflows (e.g., Pegasus, Galaxy), these platforms are generally limited to reproducing software workflows [15, 16]. To our knowledge, there are no free open-source platforms that manage entire experimental pipelines, from wet-bench experiments to bioinformatic analyses. Laboratory information management systems (LIMS) typically focus on inventory management and sample tracking and have limited capability to record experimental metadata, data analysis parameters, and for interfacing with project team members [17-19]. Although there have been several commercial efforts in this direction, they can be limited in

scope (e.g., only tracking sequencing reagents) and/or rather expensive to small academic laboratories [20, 21]. These platforms typically have limited integration between data production and a wide range of experimental metadata.

We developed the Platform for Epigenomic and Genomic Research (PEGR), a web-based project management platform that integrates wet-bench sample tracking with downstream bioinformatic workflows (managed by Galaxy.org workflows) to address the challenge of experimental reproducibility. PEGR provides end-to-end management of (epi)genomics projects from initial reagent usage through to the reproducible generation of publication-quality figures (Figure 1). PEGR logs sample information and experimental details. It manages metadata produced by Galaxy or any other workflow system and provides sample reporting and visualization. It supports Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) best practices by tracking the metadata throughout the entire sequencing pipeline to enable experimental reproducibility [22]. Previously, we presented a proof-of-concept vision of PEGR software [23]. We now present a fully functional and open-source version of PEGR software, including streamlined experiment tracking with reagent barcoding, flexibility for multiple heterogeneous bioinformatics workflows, and a project management approach. PEGR is freely available and open source at <https://github.com/seqcode/pegr>.

Figure 1. Schematic of feature integration within PEGR. The outer text represents the stages of an (epi)genomic workflow that PEGR manages. Arrows reflect workflow direction, whereas the inner text represents the conduits by which PEGR controls information flow through each stage. PEGR captures customizable metadata based upon the settings and fields set by an administrator for the platform.

Keywords—genomics;Galaxy;high-throughput sequencing;data management system;reproducibility;science

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